

Masuli characteristics are the following:

1. Higher grain yield under low-to-medium fertility.
2. Equally good yield under rainfed lowland.
3. Higher grain yield with late planting condition, even with 60-d-old seedlings.
4. Early maturity (within Nov), leaving time for farmers to plant winter crops.

5. Medium fine, soft, moist cooked grain quality accepted at almost all levels of society.
6. Intermediate tall, giving farmers straw for their cattle.
7. A 15-20% higher market price.
8. More than 32% head rice recovery.

Masuli has become susceptible to blast, particularly at the seedling stage. The fungicide carbendazim is used for its control. □

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Seed technology

Variability in rice seed vigor after storage

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We evaluated 21 shortduration rices with 3 different grain characteristics—long slender, short bold, and medium bold—for germinability after 9 mo storage in 1986-87. Details on seed viability, germination percentage, coleoptile seedling length, vigor index (germination percentage × seedling length), and dry matter production are given in the table.

The medium bold seed type cultivars had higher values for coleoptile length, seedling length, vigor index, and dry matter production than long slender types. Intragroup variability for the physiological parameters was relatively higher than intergroup variability. Intragroup variability was highest in long slender genotypes, followed by the short bold. Medium bold genotypes had the least variability.

Variability in germination and dehydrogenase enzyme activity was considerably higher in long slender genotypes than in medium bold genotypes. The higher dehydrogenase enzyme activity indicates the potential vigor of stored seeds of medium bold genotypes. □

Germination of seeds of 3 genotypes after 9-mo storage, Coimbatore, India.

Genotypes	Germination (%)		Coleoptile length (cm)	Seedling length (cm)		Vigor index	Dry matter production (mg)	Dehydrogenase activity (O.D.)
	Initial	After storage		Initial	After storage			
<i>Long slender</i>								
T2978	100	94	2.15	41.8	35.4	3302	0.0151	0.062
T2021	95	46	1.02	40.0	32.9	1547	0.0087	0.037
T1724	100	85	2.00	40.7	32.4	2771	0.0132	0.115
HY68	95	77	1.92	37.2	32.6	2521	0.0119	0.152
T2023	95	93	1.60	37.0	30.5	2847	0.0118	0.067
T358	100	89	1.50	40.7	34.2	3059	0.0152	0.067
T1814	96	84	2.37	44.1	36.9	3105	0.0132	0.155
Mean	97	83	1.79	40.0	33.5	2736	0.0127	0.093
<i>Short bold</i>								
T1727	100	74	1.70	38.4	30.9	2273	0.0146	0.075
T1406	100	74	1.57	42.4	36.2	3432	0.0179	0.142
T2952	100	97	1.70	38.7	32.8	3153	0.0185	0.087
T1769	95	82	1.40	47.5	35.3	2919	0.0214	0.125
T2006	95	93	3.29	40.7	34.1	3118	0.0169	0.127
T218	92	79	1.92	34.6	29.5	2345	0.0101	0.082
T2099	100	85	2.17	37.5	32.8	2804	0.0156	0.127
Mean	97	88	1.96	40.0	33.0	2863	0.0164	0.109
<i>Medium bold</i>								
T828	100	90	2.65	43.1	40.5	3674	0.0151	0.087
T1668	100	88	2.82	44.5	40.3	3558	0.0176	0.092
T1824	100	87	3.17	42.7	33.9	2943	0.0155	0.115
T2297	96	84	2.50	41.5	35.8	3001	0.0181	0.097
T2832	100	96	2.65	47.9	33.6	3189	0.0153	0.082
SLO 7	100	93	2.75	37.0	35.1	3278	0.0158	0.137
T1704	100	88	2.45	44.5	37.2	3330	0.0175	0.145
Mean	99	90	2.71	43.0	36.6	3281	0.0164	0.107
LSD (0.05)		9.4	0.69		2.8	443	0.0017	0.011
(0.01)		13.0	0.94		3.9	604	0.0024	0.015
Length (mm) × Width (mm)								
Long slender		7.2	×		1.6			
		8.9	×		1.6			
Short bold		4.1	×		1.8			
		6.4	×		1.8			
Medium bold		6.6	×		1.9			
		8.1	×		1.9			